

Principals' Reward Management Strategies and Teachers Productivity in Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

BY

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Abstract

The study was designed to find out the principals' reward management strategies and teachers productivity in Rivers State of Nigeria. The study adopted the correlational research design. A 15- item structured questionnaire was developed by the researcher from the three research questions formulated to elicit data for this study. The population used for the study is made up of 697 teachers selected from five public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. A sample of ten percent (71 respondents) was selected from the population for final study. Data were collected for the study through the administration of validated questionnaire to the respondents. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the test re-test method in which a correlation coefficient of 0.86 was obtained. Spearman Rho correlation statistics was used to answer the research questions and to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that principals' reward management strategies in the form of motivation, accommodation, awards correlate teacher's productivity. It was concluded that proper application of reward management strategies enhance staff productivity but inadequate application of relevant reward management strategy will hamper staff productivity and ultimately students' academic achievement. It was therefore recommended among others that school principals should be armed with adequate knowledge of various reward management strategies through seminars and in-service training in order to apply them intelligibly for maximum staff productivity in schools.

Keywords: Principal, Management, Strategy, Productivity

Introduction

In recent times, the problem most organizations are facing is the problem of how to attract and keep high quality staffs that are of competitive advantage to the organization. Most organizations lack the appropriate mechanism that will help in the recruitment, retention, motivation and development of employees so that they can perform and deliver at their highest

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potential. In line with the above scenario, organizations should develop adequate reward management strategies that will motivate employees towards achieving corporate goals.

Historically, the advent of reward management could be traced to the traditional approach of managing reward (Armstrong, 2015). During this era, the main focus of organizational managers was on salary management which lay emphasis on the need to attract, motivate and retain employees. More so, focus was on competitive attributes rather than strategic/tactical issues which reflected on how rigidly organizations were structured and managed. There was a paradigm shift from salary management to what we know today as reward management. During this era, emphasis was on performance of all employees contributing to success of the organization and paying people for the value they added to the organization (Armstrong, 2015).

Following the advent of reward management, scholars have perceived the concept in different ways. For instance, Michael (2019) saw reward management as a way of looking at strategic planning and realizing what we know all along. To him reward management provides a methodology for solving organizational problems at all levels from strategic to mundane.

In the words of Christina (2017), reward management is an aspect of human resource management which deals with the establishment, maintenance and development of a system that is aimed at rewarding the work done by employees within an organization. On a broader context, reward management concerns itself with formulating and implementing strategies and other policies that are geared towards rewarding employees of the organization. Rewarding

is aimed at being fair, equitable and consistent on the account of the particular employee's value to the organization.

Reward management is about the design, implementation, maintenance, communication and evolution of reward policies which help organizations to improve performance and achieve their objectives (Ed Merritt, 2012). Management of rewards are based on reward philosophies and strategies and contain arrangements in the shape of policies and strategies, guiding principles, practices, structures and procedures which are devised and managed to provide and maintain appropriate types and levels of pay, benefits and other forms of rewards (Bob, 2017).

Reward management also constitutes measuring job values, designing and maintaining pay structures, paying for performance, competence, skills and providing employee benefits. However, reward management is not just about pay or monetary rewards. It's also concerned with those non-financial rewards which provide intrinsic or extrinsic motivation (Bob, 2017). Organizations must reward employees because in return, they are expecting from the employees a kind of behaviour which is to work with a high level of performance and loyalty. Individual employees in return for their commitment expect certain extrinsic reward in the form of salary, promotion, fringes benefits, bonuses or stock options. They also seek intrinsic rewards such as feeling of competence, achievement, responsibility significance, influence,

personal growth, and meaningful contribution. Employees judge the adequacy of their exchange with the organization by assessing both sets of rewards (Ed Merritt, 2018).

To the researcher, reward management is that aspect of Human Resource Management (HRM) which deals with the strategic policies and processes required to ensure that the contributions of employees to the organization are recognized and rewarded both financially and non-financial means. To this effect, reward management is aimed at developing and maintaining a high performance culture among employees within an organization. Also reward management can be seen as a segment of HRM which focuses on planning, organizing, directing, and coordinating the affairs of staff as it correlates to monetary and none monetary rewards as it affects their job performance in achieving organizational goals.

Some of the reward management strategies as propounded by Armstrong (2015) are as follows:

- **Base pay strategy:** This strategy comprises of short-term and long term incentive, base salary/wage, premium Pay, cash recognition, annual bonuses, shares and profit sharing.
- **Benefits Rewards:** This strategy includes health care, retirement (pensions) and work like benefits; this account for an increasing portion of the reward package for employees.
- **Career rewards:** These include training and development, lateral move/advancement, stretch assignments, personal growth via career incentives and employment security.

- **Non-financial rewards:** This strategy includes recognition, praise, achievement, responsibility and professional growth, a pleasant working environment, being involved in decisions that affect how and when employees do their work, creative rewards etc.
- **Total reward management strategy:** This is the combination of all other reward management strategies that are available to the employer (Armstrong, 2015).

The ability of school managers/principals to use these strategies effectively so as to increase performance and enhance efficiency depends on the extent to which he or she adopts appropriate strategy channel.

In review of reward management strategies adopted in secondary schools, it is observed that teachers have a lot of differences in performing their duties as regards to how they are motivated financially and none financially. Inadequacy and improper management strategies adopted in most schools in channeling the available materials to administer the rewarding practices hinders most teachers from deriving maximum satisfaction in the execution of their functions, leading to poor performance. It is as a result of this that the researcher is in quest to review the reward management strategies adopted by some secondary school principals in Rivers State with the aim of identifying how it has influenced staff productivity.

Statement of the Problem

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Records have shown that many organizations in Nigeria in general and Rivers State in particular hardly reward their staff for excellent productivity which is attributed to their unfamiliarity with reward management strategies. This has greatly reduced staff productivity which is evident in the poor academic achievement of their students. It is quite obvious that some secondary school students in Rivers State can no longer face boldly the educational challenges and this is attributable to staff poor performance. Most staff (teachers) exhibit nonchalant attitudes to teaching their students, some even leave their places of work for other unofficial business during official hours while others that are around will stay idle in the staff-room chatting and gisting, leaving their students at the mercy of their own faith. The few who manage to teach, do it with I don't care attitude because to them the school managers do not appreciate, recognize, praise nor encourage their good deeds so as to motivate them to do more.

The core reason for this downward trend in staff productivity is that there are no adequate measures taken by most secondary schools authorities in implementing appropriate reward strategy which could be of help to motivate staff in putting in their best in job performance. To this end, the researcher intends to examine principals' reward management strategies and teacher's productivity in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

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The aim of this study is to examine principals' reward management strategies and teacher's productivity in secondary schools in Rivers State; Specifically, this study was carried out to:

1. Examine the relationship between teachers motivation and teachers productivity in secondary schools.
2. Determine the relationship between provision of teachers accommodation and teachers productivity in secondary schools.
3. Ascertain the relationship between giving teachers awards and teachers productivity in secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the relationship between teachers motivation and teachers productivity in secondary schools?
2. What is the relationship between provision of teachers accommodation and teachers productivity in secondary schools?
3. What is the relationship between giving teacher's awards and teacher's productivity in secondary schools?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho1: there is no significant relationship between teachers motivation and teachers productivity in secondary schools.

Ho2: there is no significant relationship between provision of teachers accommodation and teachers productivity in secondary schools?

Ho3: there is no significant relationship between giving teacher's awards and teacher's productivity in secondary schools?

Method

This study utilized descriptive survey research design to investigate the population of the study and the schools selected to enhance proper data collection and analysis. The researcher chose this design because the study involved collection and analysis of opinions and responses of secondary school teachers and principals in a given area.

The population of the study covers a total of 697 respondents made up of 10 principals and 687 staff from the ten selected secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The researcher chose the sample size of 25% to reduce the population to a more manageable size for easy data interpretation and analysis. The proportional sampling

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techniques was used to get the sample from the population. This was obtained by randomly selecting 25% of teachers' population in each of the schools under investigation.

The instrument that was used to elicit data for this study is structured research questionnaire by the researcher. The questionnaire was divided into two (2) parts. Part I deals with the background information of the respondents which encompasses such data as name of school, gender, academic qualification, type of ownership, while the Part II contains items on the research objectives. Twenty-four questionnaire items were used and the responses are structured on a 4-point rating scale, and the structured rating type questionnaire is designed as follows: Strongly- Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (DA) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The reliability of the instrument was determined using the test re-test method. Data obtained was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Formula and a correlation coefficient of 0.86 was obtained. The research instrument was administered directly by the researcher to different schools selected for this study. Spearman Rho Correlation Formula was used to answer the research questions and to test the hypothesis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT

Demography Analysis

Table 1 Gender of the respondents

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Variable	Frequency	Percent
Male	44	61.9
Female	27	38.1
Total	71	100.0

Table 1 shows that 44 respondents representing 61.9% of the sample were males while 27(38.1%) were females.

Table 2 Age of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent
25-29	17	23.9
30-35	30	42.2
36-49	10	14.1
50-55	9	12.7
55 and above	5	7.1
Total	71	100.0

Table 2 shows that 17 respondents representing 23.9% of the sample were between 25 – 29 years, 30(42.2%) were between 30 – 35 years, 10(14.1%) were between 36 – 49 years, 10(12.7%) were between 50 – 55 years while 5(7.1%) were 55 years and above.

Table 3 Marital Status of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Single	30	42.3
Married	39	54.9
Divorced	2	2.8
Total	71	100.0

Table 3 revealed that 30 respondents representing 42.3% of the sample were single, 39(54.9%) were married while 2(2.8%) were divorced.

Table 4 Educational qualification

Variable	Frequency	Percent
B.Sc	39	54.9
Masters	21	31.2
Doctorate	10	14.8
Others	0	0

Table 4 shows that 39 respondents representing 54.9% of the sample had Bachelor’s degrees, 21(31.2%) had Masters degrees, 10(14.8%) had Doctorate degrees.

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between teachers motivation and teachers productivity in secondary schools?

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers motivation and teachers productivity in secondary schools.

Table 1 Correlation analysis on relationship between teachers motivation and teachers productivity in secondary schools.

		Teachers motivation	Productivity
Spearman's rho	Teachers motivation	1.000	.85
	Correlation Coefficient		.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	71	71
Productivity	Productivity	.85	1.000
	Correlation Coefficient		.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	71	71

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 5: reveals a correlation coefficient of 0.85. This coefficient shows that a positive relationship exist between Teachers motivation and Productivity in in secondary schools. The Spearman's rho table reveals p value of 0.000 and a sig. value of 0.05. Hence, since the sig value ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) is lesser than 0.05 alpha therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected

meaning there is a relationship between Teachers motivation and Productivity in secondary schools.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between provision of teachers accommodation and teachers productivity in secondary schools?

H02: There is no significant relationship between provision of teachers accommodation and teachers productivity in secondary schools.

Table 2 Correlation analysis on relationship between provision of teachers accommodation and teachers productivity in secondary schools.

		Teachers accommodation	Teachers productivity
Spearman's rho	Teachers accommodation	1.000	.81
	Correlation Coefficient		.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)		71
	N	71	71
	Teachers productivity	.81	1.000
	Correlation Coefficient	.000	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		71
	N	71	71

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 5: reveals a correlation coefficient of 0.81. This coefficient shows that a positive relationship exist between provision of teachers accommodation and teachers productivity in secondary schools. The Spearman's rho table reveals p value of 0.000 and a sig. value of 0.05.

Hence, since the sig value ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) is lesser than 0.05 alpha therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected meaning there is a relationship between provision of teachers accommodation and teachers productivity in secondary schools.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between giving teacher’s awards and teacher’s productivity in secondary schools?

H02: There is no significant relationship between giving teacher’s awards and teacher’s productivity in secondary schools.

Table 2 Correlation analysis on relationship between giving teacher’s awards and teacher’s productivity in secondary schools.

		Teachers awards	Teachers productivity
Spearman's rho	Teachers awards	1.000	.79
	Correlation Coefficient		.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	71	71
Teachers productivity	Teachers productivity	.79	1.000
	Correlation Coefficient		.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	71	71

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 5: reveals a correlation coefficient of 0.79. This coefficient shows that a positive relationship exist between giving teacher's awards and teacher's productivity in secondary schools. The Spearman's rho table reveals p value of 0.000 and a sig. value of 0.05. Hence, since the sig value ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) is lesser than 0.05 alpha therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected meaning there is a relationship between giving teacher's awards and teacher's productivity in secondary schools.

Discussions

The result of the analysis of Research Question 1 revealed that relationship between teachers motivation and teachers productivity in secondary schools. The finding is in line with the assertion of Ezinne (2012) that motivation can basically be cash compensation or reward that an employer gives for the work performed which reflects the value of work or skills. It is the function of the skill or education an employee possesses.

The data result in Research Question 2 shows that there is a relationship between provision of teachers accommodation and teachers productivity in secondary schools. The finding is in accordance with the assertion of Chartered Instituted of Personnel and Development, CIPD (2016) that the core aim of fringe accommodation to employees is to develop a healthy climate for employer-employee relationship, minimize excessive labour

turnover costs and provide a feeling of individual security against hazards and problems of life with a view to eventually enhancing employee loyalty to company and improving productivity. (CIPD 2016) on the other hand observed that there are various reasons why employers offer employees accommodation, some of which are to match with market practice, for other it is to provide employees with some measure of security.

The result analysis in Research Question 4 shows that there is relationship between giving teacher's awards and teacher's productivity in secondary schools. This finding is in line with the findings of McCormick and Tifflin (1979) which they called intrinsic rewards, as rewards that are inherent in job itself and which the individuals enjoy as a result of successfully completing the task or attaining his goals. They went further to term this type of reward as "psychological rewards", giving examples as opportunity to use one's ability, a sense of challenge, and achievement, receiving appreciation, positive recognition, and being treated in a caring and considerate manner. Nadia, Syed and Humera (2012) also opined to this reward as internal or psychological rewards which can be in terms of appreciation, meeting the new challenges, positive and caring attitude from employer, and job rotation after attaining the goal.

Conclusions

Based on the finding of the study, it can therefore be concluded that various rewards management strategies such as motivation, accommodation and awards hold remarkable

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influence on staff productivity in secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. It revealed that when school staff are adequately rewarded by enhanced salaries/wages, provided with avenue and financial support for skill update and careers advancement in their various fields of learning, accommodations to meet up with the cost incurred in the provision of life necessities and given recognition and encouragement, it releases in them the motivation to put in their best towards achieving set goals and objectives.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, discussions and conclusion drawn from it, the following recommendations are made:

- Principals and school proprietors/proprietresses should ensure that the staff is adequately rewarded using different reward management strategies to improve their performance on their job.
- Government should organize seminars and workshop for principals and private school owners with the aim of equipping them with relevant reward management strategies in order to get the best of their staff.

- Since all the reward management strategies may not be suitable at all time, principals should take time to analyze situations and events in order to determine the best reward management strategy that would be most rewarding and effective at any given time.
- Adequate fund should be made available for school principals by government and school proprietors/proprietresses as the case may be, for prompt response to occasions that demand staff rewards and remuneration.
- Government should provide relevant legislation with respect to staff welfare in the form of minimum wage beyond which no private school proprietor/proprietress should pay their workers
- Principals and school owners should arm themselves with various reward management strategies through self-development materials and training in order to motivate their staff for optimum performance.
- Government and private school owners should adopt a standard of reviewing and periodic adjustment of secondary schools staff salaries to meet up with economic changes and inflationary rate.

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